

ASSESSMENT OF GAS EMISSIONS ON ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION AS ENABLERS FOR A CLEANER ENVIRONMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

Egbivwie, Ejiroghene Steffi, PhD

Department of Business Administration, College of Management and Social Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria.

Steffi.egbivwe@gvu.edu.ng

09056668204

&

Osondu Chidozie Roland

Department of Business Administration, College of Management and Social Sciences, Glorious Vision University,

Email: osonduroland@gvu.edu.ng

Phone Number; 07033947778

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Abstract:

This paper discusses the assessment of gas emissions on environmental conservation as enablers for a cleaner environment and economic growth in Nigeria. It seeks to examine the effect of environmental conservation on sustainable economic growth. Survey research design was adopted in the study. Nigeria Gas Company was used as a case study. The total number of staff at the Nigerian Gas Company was four hundred and eighty (480). Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size of two hundred and eighteen (218). Data obtained were analysed with the use of linear regression. We found components of gas emission such as oxides of nitrogen, carbon and sulphur, hydrocarbons and ash, hydrogen sulphide, and photochemical oxidants with negative effect on the environment, economic, and human health. It was also found that flare stack, safety shutdown system and emergency depressurization system are enablers for environmental conservation. The study recommends provision of environmental laws and regulation to mitigate gas emission as well as enacting national regulatory framework on the environment.

Keywords- Environmental, conservation, economic growth, gas flare, greenhouse, climate change.

Introduction

Nigerian Gas Company contributed to the conservation of the environment for quality of life, sustainable economic growth, and a good atmosphere that is free from severe environmental damages, product and financial losses, loss of plants, corrosion, diseases, and flooding. It also contributed to the development of an efficient gas industry to fully serve the nation's energy and industrial feedstock. It creates investment opportunities for entrepreneurs. Global warming is the increase in the average temperature of the earth near surface air and oceans in recent decades and its projected continuation (Muhammad & Mohammed, 2008).

Brännlund and Lundgren (2009), claim that better environmental regulation increases resource use efficiency and under some conditions, can increase economic performance. In addition, environmental regulations also motivate firms to adopt new technologies, which may increase economic growth in the long run (Fan & Hao, 2020). Environmental regulations influence economic performance, individual, communities, and society quality. In fact, the tradeoff between economic performance and environmental protection is essential, especially in less abundant countries (Sarkodie & Strezov, 2019). Environmental preservation and global climate crisis must be considered by various organizations, communities, and individuals that are concerned. Anwaret *et al.*, 2022) reveal that economic and political freedoms indicate systemic differences across countries and are shown to significantly affect environmental degradation, as well as the preferences and costs of environmental protection. Environmental protection involves monitoring of personal behaviour, communities, and industrial regulations through all kinds of surveillance means to increase the efficiency of environmental regulations and quality for good economic

performance. Boyle, 2007) states that environmental regulations must be implemented in a way that does not clearly restrict individual freedom.

Statement of the Problem

Environmental issues occur at both the global level and in communities. Issues of flaring and venting of gas can contribute to major environmental problems and become disastrous if they are not properly handled. Gas flaring degrades the environment, resulting in product and financial losses, reputational damage, and putting people and assets at risk. Gas flares are one of the major culprits implicated in the issue of environmental climate change, commonly addressed as global warming. It destroys natural resources and produces harmful waste that is hazardous to society. Flaring and venting of gas contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, which have a negative impact on the environment. Greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxides, troposphere ozone, chlorofluorocarbons, nitrogen oxide, methane, and fluorocarbons are known to emit and absorb radiation. They also circulate in the atmosphere and act as a thick blanket over the planet, causing global warming. Global warming melts the polar ice, causing flood problems, coastal inundation, ecological destabilization, and sea level rise. It gradually increases the temperature of the earth's lower atmosphere due to an increase in greenhouse gases since the industrial revolution. This study therefore determines the role of the Nigeria Gas Company in environmental conservation. There has been a lot of research done over the centuries on environmental conservation in different organisations and countries, but none on the specific gas company under study in South-South Nigeria, thus, creating a knowledge gap for research. Hence, the study looks at the assessment of gas emissions on environmental conservation as enablers for a cleaner environment and economic growth in Nigeria

Objective of the Problem

The specific objective of the problem is sought:

1. to examine the effect of environmental conservation on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

Environmental Issues in Nigeria

The requirements to sustain the environment and tackle its challenges remain urgent and cannot be overemphasized. The Nigeria Gas Company, in an attempt to flare gas, contributes to emissions of carbon monoxide, nitrogen (II) oxide, and methane, which are estimated to account for 1 to 4 percent of the total emissions from all sources of hazardous discharges, unnecessary heat, and light, affecting nearby environments, towns, communities, and surroundings. This activity is one of the major environmental issues in Nigeria and in some oil-producing parts of the world. The threat of climate change is a source of concern to the Nigerian Gas Company. The increasing levels of carbon dioxide emissions and the by-products of the incessant drive towards industrialization are a threat to human livelihoods and resources. Also, other heat-trapping greenhouse gases (GHGs) are being added from nitrous oxide in nitrogen fertilizer. It is a difficult task for nations with low technological acquisitions to cope with the effects without causing damage to their sustainability capabilities. In various ways, Nigeria has depended immensely on carbon-based fuels, which add carbon dioxide to the atmosphere to trap heat from the sun. The temperature of the atmosphere near the earth's surface, which is warmed through a natural process called the greenhouse effect, Short-wave light visibly comes from the sun to the earth, passing unimpeded through a blanket of thermal or greenhouse gases composed of water vapor, carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, and ozone. Infrared radiation reflects off the planet's surface towards space and does not easily pass through the thermal blanket. Some of it is trapped and reflected downward, keeping the planet at an average temperature suitable for life of about 600 °F (160 °C) (IPCC, 1990).

Conceptualization of the Environment

The environment is seen as everything around us, including all of the living and nonliving things with which we interact. Despite our many scientific and technological advances, we are utterly dependent on the environment for air, water, food, shelter, energy, and everything else we need to stay alive and healthy. As

a result, we are part of and not apart from the rest of nature (Miller and Spoolman, 2008). Environmental protection awareness and practices are encouraged at all times to properly treat the environment. There is a need to respond to ecological studies, such as those on the environment and life. Environmental protection awareness and practices require knowledge, understanding, a change of attitude, and participation in actions (Silva *et al.*, 2018). Increasing the level of environmental protection is crucial to overcoming environmental problems.

Conceptualization of Conservation

Miller and Spoolman, (2008), state that conservation is the management of natural resources with the goal of minimizing resource waste and sustaining supplies for current and future generations. Conservation is a discipline that attempts to prescribe methods for maintaining and restoring biodiversity. This relatively new field embraces four fundamental objectives supporting the overarching goal of maintaining and protecting the native biodiversity of a region in perpetuity. Protecting and maintaining ecosystems is widely known as essential to protecting public health and the environment. Many government efforts now know that clean air and hygiene water depend not only on the control of hazardous emissions but also on the maintenance of ecosystem services that accumulate waste.

Components of Gas Flare

Nigeria is the largest producer of crude oil in Africa and the 15th largest producer in the world, producing on a daily average about 2.2 million barrels (Climate Institution Association, 2010), and this accounts for over 90%–95% of Nigeria's foreign earnings and government revenues, respectively. As a result of this huge oil production, Nigeria is one of the oil-producing countries that introduce greenhouse gases through gas flaring into the environment, changing the state of the environment. Nigeria had the second-largest gas flaring volume—about 15 billion cube meters (BCM)—after Russia, according to the estimation (Elvidge *et al.*, 2009).

Petroleum is a naturally occurring complex mixture that contains predominantly hydrocarbon compounds with a frequent content of significant amounts of nitrogen, sulfur, and oxygen, together with a smaller quantity of nickel, vanadium, and various elements. Petroleum compounds occur in solid form as asphalt, in liquid form as crude oil, and in gaseous form as natural gas. Petroleum hydrocarbons could be divided into four classes: saturates (pentane, hexadecane, octacosane, and cyclohexane), aromatics (naphthalene, phenanthrene, benzene, and pyrene), asphaltenes (phenols, fatty acids, ketones, esters, and porphyrins), and resins (pyridines, quinolines, carbozoles, sulfoxides, and amides) (Ite & Semple, 2012).

The ultimate sink for most petroleum contaminants is both soil and sediments, such as benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, and xylenes (BTEX), as well as aliphatic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Petroleum hydrocarbon contaminants of soils and sediment are a global concern because of the toxicity and refractory character of the aromatic components in the absence of oxygen. The occurrence of gas flaring in the Nigerian Gas Company is an issue that cannot be fully understood without considering the innumerable life- and environment-threatening effects it brings along. Environmental contamination of air, water, soil, and food through gas flaring has become a disaster to the continued existence of many plants, animals, and communities, ultimately threatening the very survival of people living in that community as well as the neighboring communities. Gases such as CO₂, SO₂, NO₂, etc. are emitted in the process. While most of these gases are critical pollutants, others are greenhouse gases. The oxides of sulfur and nitrogen from the flared gas combine with water in the atmosphere to form various types of corrosive acids that alter and damage various soil parameters (Ubuoh, 2011).

Conceptualization of Economic Growth

Muritala, (2011) reveals that economic growth is the use of technological advancement and institutional and ideological adjustment to supply increasingly diverse economic goods to its population. Economic growth of any nation cannot be over emphasized. The determination of an economy and its sustainability generates immediate financial assistance and capabilities for national continuous development. Economic

growth refers to quantifiable and constant increase in a nation's per capital income through trade volume, time, increased labour force, and consumption capital. It includes the increase in the gross national product and services, also income per person. Economic growth can be positive (expansion) or negative (contraction) depending on the values of current and past national output as given by the gross domestic product (Amoako & Insaideo, 2021). Economic growth signifies increase in industrial and agricultural activities, rise in fossil fuel use, deforestation, environmental degradation, land reclamation, pollution, etc

Environmental Conservation and Economic Growth

Anwar et al., (2022), state that an economic and political freedom have been shown to affect the environment significantly regarding the preferences for and costs of environmental protection.

The Gross Domestic Product measures the increase in economic activities of a nation and the increase in the GDP means more use of nonrenewable energies and greenhouse gas emissions to the environment. The economic performance in poorer countries leads to a decrease in environmental quality, the association is reversed in richer countries (Anwar et al., 2022). The greenhouse gases add to the greenhouse possible effect as it absorbs infrared radiation. The natural process that warms the surface of the Earth is affected by the greenhouse. This is when the energy of the sun touches the earth's atmosphere, some reflect to space, while some is absorbed and reradiated by the greenhouse gases. The Earth surface and the atmosphere are warmed by the absorbed energy, giving way to life on Earth to exist. The greenhouse gases include carbon dioxide, methane, ozone, chlorofluorocarbons, and nitrous oxide. Mitigating environmental degradation is very crucial to economic growth. (Dechezleprêtre, et al., 2022) reveal that environmental regulations motivate firms to adopt new technologies, which may increase economic growth in the long run.

Mitigation strategies can be adopted to address the challenges of climate change affecting the environment, thereby paving way for more economic growth. (EKC, Shahbaz et al., 2013), argue that the relationships between economic growth and environmental quality may change the sign when the country reaches a certain level of economic performance as people can afford more efficient and environment-friendly production resulting in a cleaner environment as suggested by Environmental Kuznets Curve. Environmental conservation enhances a lot of societal achievements like climate change mitigation, increase revenues, building of new industries, long-term sustainability of living, encourages new technologies, a cleaner environment, and healthier food for increase in economic performance. (Brännlund and Lundgren, 2009), reveal that a better environmental regulation increases resource use efficiency and, under some conditions, can increase economic performance.

Effect of Greenhouse

Gas flaring contributes enormous amount of greenhouse gases, hence causing climate change (IPCC, 2001). Greenhouse effect is the process by which radiative energy leaving a planetary surface is absorbed by some atmospheric gases known as greenhouse gases. The Sun is Earth's only external form of heat. It emits solar radiation mainly in the form of shortwave visible and ultraviolet (UV) energy. As this radiation travels toward the Earth, about 25 percent of the radiated energy is absorbed by the atmosphere and about 25 percent is reflected by the clouds and other gases back into space. The remaining radiation travels unimpeded to the Earth and heats its surface. The atmosphere acts like the glass in a glass greenhouse, making much of the shortwave solar radiation to pass through unimpeded, but trapping many of the long wave heat energy trying to escape back to space. The greenhouse gases transfer the energy to the surface and lower atmosphere and it is reradiated in all directions, including down towards the Earth's surface. In this way, the temperature rises in the atmosphere just as it does in the artificial greenhouse.

Earth's Natural Greenhouse Gases

The Earth's greenhouse gases do not constitute any harm to the environment in their natural state of occurrence. The Earth's natural greenhouse effect transfers energy to the Earth's surface and lower atmosphere; so that the temperature there is higher than it would have been if direct heating by solar radiation were the only warming mechanism. This process has a warming effect of about 33°C, without which the Earth will be uninhabitable. The major natural greenhouse gases are: water vapour which causes 36%-70% of greenhouse effect; carbon dioxide, CO₂, 9%-26%; methane CH₄ 4%-9% and ozone with 3%-7% (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/global_warming).

Greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide and other discharged pollutants, collect in the atmosphere, trap heat from the sun and cause the planet to warm. Global warming has adverse effects on weather patterns, ecological system, human health, wildlife, sea levels, polar ice, and the glaciers. With the use of less energy, the demands on power plants are reduced, resulting in less pollution. Couple energy conservation with increasing your reliance on renewable energy sources, and you can reduce greenhouse emissions and help stop global warming (Natural Resources Defense Council, 2005).

Gas Flare and Vent

Gas flaring and venting are both widely used in the oil and natural gas industry to dispose of associated natural gases for safety reasons during petroleum development operations and/or where no infrastructure exists to bring it to market. The process of flaring (burning) and venting (releasing into the atmosphere without burning) of petroleum associated gas has been dramatically curbed in developed countries. Although Norway has adopted flaring reduction measures and introduced a carbon tax, gas flaring and venting minimization strategies in Nigeria seem difficult over the past years. The extent of economic loss due to gas flaring and venting is estimated at \$2.5 billion annually and enormous economic benefits would

have accrued to the Nigerian government from harnessing this energy resource (Buzcu-Guven & Harriss, 2012). Gas flaring and venting associated with petroleum exploration and production in the Nigeria's Niger Delta has continued to generate complex consequences in terms of energy, human health, natural environment, socio-economic environment and sustainable development over the past fifty years (Ite & Ibok, 2013).

Flaring of associated gas mainly emits carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and a variety of air pollutants, such as volatile organic compounds (VOC) which include carcinogens and air toxics, nitrogen oxides (NO₂), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), toxic heavy metals, and black carbon soot. Gas flaring and venting in the oil-producing areas of Niger Delta and vehicular traffic emissions (CO₂, HC, NO₂, SO₂ and particulate matters) add to the atmospheric pollution. Ologunorisa, empirical studies on the impact of gas flaring on the physical, soil, chemical, biological, atmospheric and social environment have not been adequately documented. In spite of decree 99, which bans unauthorized flaring, Nigeria flares over 75 percent of the associated gas it produces and this represents a pollution equivalent to 45 million tons of CO₂ per day. Currently, Nigeria has over 123 flaring sites in the Niger Delta region and has been regarded as one of the highest emitter of greenhouse gases in Africa (Uyigue & Agho, 2007). Some 45.8 billion kilowatts of heat are discharged into the atmosphere of the Niger Delta from combustion of 1.8 billion cubic feet of gas every day and this is a major contributing factor to the global warming crises. Further, it is known that incomplete combustion of petroleum associated gases produces a variety of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Kostiuk, *et al*, 2004).

Gas flaring precipitates global climate change and greenhouse-effect resulting in gradual rise in atmospheric temperature and depletion of the ozone layer (the natural cooling shield from sun rays insulation and heat in the sky), thereby exposing the earth to high intensity of solar radiation, the impacts of these environmental threat include food insecurity, increasing risk of disease, acid rain, rain corrosion of buildings and the rising costs of extreme weather damage because of the presence of widely-recognized toxins, such as benzene in the air (Idris, 2007).

The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) and major scientific organizations of industrialized countries concluded that the rise in global temperature since the middle of twentieth century has been because of mainly human induced (anthropogenic) greenhouse gases concentration via the greenhouse effect; while the warming effect of natural phenomenon like solar variation constituted a small warming effect from preindustrial times to 1950, and from then a reverse cooling effect. The United Nations Framework on climate change (UNFCCC) uses the term “Climate Variability” which is used for changes due to External Forcing (External forcing is climate change caused by change in the global energy balance owing to fluctuations in the Earth’s orbit, ocean circulation and atmospheric composition) (<http://www.ipcc.ch>, 2014).

Impact of Gas Flare on the Environment

Globally, the effect of gas flaring on the climate system is now a burning issue. The associated gas flared into the atmosphere contains some GHGs that have the potential to cause global warming, such as methane (CH₄), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), etc. (see IPCC, 2001). Nigerian natural gas contains a higher percentage of methane on the basis of molar composition than any other chemical compound (Sonibare & Akeredolu, 2004), so this makes it more dangerous to climate systems and health than natural gas from any other country. Flaring not only has an effect on the climate system, but it also has economic, social, and environmental impacts on humans and the environment. The practice of gas flaring in Nigeria is so obvious that it can be identified by satellites from space using Google Earth. The data for the satellite is from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the National Geophysical Data Centre (http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/dmsp/interest/gas_flares_countries_kmz.html, 2015).

Apart from being potential greenhouse gases, flared-associated gases comprise other carcinogenic substances such as dioxins, benzene, toluene, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, and particulate matter. When

these substances mix together with moisture in the atmosphere, an acid rain is formed, which is corrosive, harmful, and dangerous to the entire ecosystem. It can also destroy buildings by tarnishing the paintings, corroding the roofing, and seriously affecting the surrounding wetlands. This hazardous impact will militate against the efforts of the UN to conserve biodiversity and forest resources. This impact will affect the efforts of Nigeria to mitigate its influence on climate change. Nigeria has recorded a huge revenue loss due to gas flaring and oil spillage (Effiong & Etowa, 2012).

Bassey (2008) made projections on the losses that the Niger Delta might encounter due to its vulnerability to climate change impacts as a result of gas flaring. The projection has it that the Niger Delta ecosystem will lose its 50 percent ability to produce cereals by 2020, which would rise to about 8 percent in 2050 if the flaring continues. These projections look apocalyptic, and when they occur, they will be worse than any armistice conflict that has ever happened in the Niger Delta. Gas flaring, together with oil spillage, will not only result in poor crop yields in the Niger Delta but will also affect the entire fish population and other aquatic life. When the formed acid rain drops into the bodies of water, the ecological and physiochemical conditions in the aquatic environment will change, resulting in a severe negative impact on the lives of those in the marine environment.

Impact of Climate Change on the Environment

The cumulative of unchecked emission of greenhouse gases, the resultant effect, and the continuous depletion of the protective ozone layer result to deleterious changes in the global climatic conditions and are characterized by increases in earth's temperature global warming. A global temperature rise cause increase in intensity of extreme weather events, threatening natural habitats, and change in the amount and pattern of precipitation, general rise in sea level and consequent flooding of coastal land as a result of melting of the polar ice sheet. Other effects of global warming are changes in agricultural yields as a result of climate change, decrease in stream flows, economic loss, species extinctions as ecological niches disappear, and increases in the ranges of disease vector. Disruption of drinking water supplies dependent on

snow melts and more frequent tropical storms etc. are also included. There is also evidence that glaciers are retreating worldwide, that the Arctic Sea ice is thinning, and that the incidence of extreme weather events is increasing in some parts of the world owing to global warming (Watson, 2000).

In addition, the fate of many islands and coastal cities will be certainly undecided. A lot of islands will be submerged following rising sea levels and incursion of sea waters to the land. Everyone living in and around coastal areas would probably relocate until projects are put up to hold back the seas from transgressing onshore. The forests which filter the air, wetlands which are good nesting grounds for many biodiversity and water bodies which are rich in biodiversity would be put at risk as well. Bush and forest fires may become more frequent and more intense (Watson, 2000). There will be prolonged drought in many regions, while others will experience heavier rainfall. Severe storms, floods and hurricane will occur. Increasing deaths, displacements, and economic losses projected due to extreme weather attributed to global warming may be exacerbated by growing population densities in affected areas, although temperate regions are projected to experience some minor benefits, such as fewer deaths due to cold exposure (IPCC, 2007).

Additional anticipated effects include sea level rise of 110 to 770 millimeters (0.36 – 2.5ft) between 1990 and 2100 (Church, 2001). Others include repercussions to agriculture, possible slowing of the thermocline circulation, reductions in the ozone layer, increased intensity and frequency of hurricanes, lowering of ocean pH, and the spread of diseases such as malaria and dengue fever. 18% of a sample of 1,103 animal and plant species would be extinct by 2050 (Thomas, 2004).

Measures to Mitigate Gas Flare on Environment

UN (2016) states that the economic and technological development of any nation is strongly connected to energy, which is the foremost contributor to climate change accounting for around 60% of total global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Gas being flared may come from a variety of sources. It may be in excess of that which can be supplied commercially to customers. It may be unburned process gas from the processing facilities. It may be vapors collected from the tops of tanks as they are filled. Sometimes, the gas may be from process upsets, equipment changeovers, or maintenance. Occasionally, a production shutdown may require the temporary flaring of all the gas stored on or arriving at a facility to release high pressure and avoid a catastrophic situation occurring. Giwa *et al.*, (2017) state that since the mid-1990s, the country has been using natural gas for industrial energy demand and public electricity generation as a measure to utilize and reduce gas flaring. It is in the oil company's interest to realize as much value as possible from the hydrocarbon accumulations the company is producing. Therefore, it is also in the company's interest to minimize the amount of gas being flared. In this respect, the commercial aims of the company are consistent with good environmental practices.

Flare Stack

Eman, 2015) reveals that gas flaring has to do with the combustion of associated, unwanted or excess gases and liquids produced during normal operation or sudden over-pressuring operation in industrial processes, example, oil & gas extraction, refineries, chemical, plants, coal industry, etc. The purpose of a flare stack is to remove unwanted constituents out of a waste gas stream through the means of thermal oxidation or burning. A flare stack is a tall vertical vent pipe used in petroleum refineries, petrochemical plants, chemical plants, and natural gas processing plants for burning off flammable gas released by pressure relief valves during unplanned over-pressuring of plant equipment. However, a great deal of flaring has nothing to do with protection against the dangers of overpressuring industrial plant equipment. When crude oil is extracted and produced

from oil wells, raw natural gas associated with the oil is produced on the surface as well. In areas of the world lacking pipelines and other gas transportation infrastructure, vast amounts of such associated gas are commonly flared as waste or unusable gas.

Safety Shutdown System

The safety shutdown system (SSS) shall shut down the facilities to a safe state in case of an emergency situation, thus protecting personnel, the environment, and the asset. The safety shutdown system shall manage all inputs relative to emergency shutdown (ESD) functions (environment and personnel protection). This system might also be fed by signals from the main fire and gas system (Yemen LNG, 2015).

Emergency Depressurization (EDP)

Due to the closing of Emergency Shutdown ESD valves in a process, there may be some trapped flammable fluids, and these must be released in order to avoid any undesired consequences, such as a pressure increase in vessels and piping. For this, emergency depressurization (EDP) systems are used in conjunction with emergency shutdown (ESD) systems to release fluids to a safe location and in a safe manner, such as trapped fluids (Yemen LNG, 2015).

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research method. Questionnaire primary source of data was used. Appropriate statistical technique comprises simple percentage and linear regression was used to analyze the data. The total number of staff at the Nigerian Gas Company was 480. Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size of two hundred and eighteen (218). A total of two hundred and eighteen (218) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, out of which two hundred and fifteen (215) copies

representing 99% were returned and used, while three (3) copies representing 1% were not returned and used.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.625 ^a	.391	.384	1.05201	.391	59.597	1	93	.000	1.787

a. Predictors: (Constant), ENVCONS

b. Dependent Variable: ECOGROWT

Discussion of Result

It is a table and percentage observed and expected frequencies (counts) of the organization and five category response options. The responses of agree and strongly agree had more frequency counts than strongly disagree, disagree and undecided. From the table above, linear regression tests were computed. The result shows that climate change has impact on economic loss because the significant of exchange is 0.000 which is less than 0.05, so at 5% it's significant. And there is no auto-correlation in the model. The R Square shows that it is able to show 282.9% variation in the dependent variable. Using the rule of thumb, the Durbin-Watson is equal to 2%. For a result to be relevance or good, the Durbin-Watson must be up to 2%, and now we have 2%. The researcher strongly supports the finding because every nation needs economic growth and concern about the increasing depletion of the environment as a result of continues increase in global carbon dioxide emissions as well as other greenhouse gases released into the environment. This includes final

applications in industry, the generation of heat and power, construction, buildings, and transportation. The environmental pollution affects economic growth when considered as input and a by-product of production (Ricci, 2007). The technological and economic development of a nation is highly linked to energy as the primary contributor to climate change. Energy usage contributes mostly to the atmospheric emissions of the greenhouse gaseous emissions. The Fourth National Climate Assessment report of the United States, published in 2018, cautioned that if greenhouse gases are not reduced, climate change could severely interrupt the world's economies (USGCRP, 2018).

Conclusion

Emissions of greenhouse gases into the environment caused by human action occurring at an unprecedented rate require conservation and protection to enhance wildlife. The oil exploration in the region has a direct impact felt by everyone living in the area, and there is a need for appropriate compensation. Conservation of gas flares and other hazardous discharges against adverse effects on human life and the environment, strengthening public health, and environmental engineering defenses against diseases and catastrophes. Some of these issues include ecological degradation, flooding, environmental pollution, associated human rights abuses, high inflation, health challenges, and loss of livelihood. Protecting the environment, modern society, natural ecosystems, human life, water resources, socio-economic activities, infrastructure, the climate, agriculture, forestry, and fisheries against gas emissions, which are caused mainly by human activities and to enhance public welfare.

Gas flares contribute a substantial amount of greenhouse gases released into the environment, increasing climate change, which results in coastal inundation, ecological degradation and destabilization, melting of the polar ice, acid rain, floods, health challenges, sea level rise, and economic loss. Inadequate knowledge of gas emissions in the environment threatens natural habitats, human livelihoods, and resources. Gas

flaring causes degradation of the environment and contaminants the atmosphere with oxides of nitrogen, carbon, and sulfur, hydrocarbons and ash, hydrogen sulfide, photochemical oxidants, and other hazardous discharges, acidifying the soil to deplete the nutrient and nutritional value of crops, making the environment neither habitable nor suitable for human consumption. Acid rain, caused by gas emissions, decays building materials, acidifies water and soil, harms human health, and damages vegetables. The reluctance of policymakers to respond to gas emissions increases climate change and has a negative impact on human life.

Recommendation

Based on the study of the role of Nigerian Gas Company in environmental conservation, it would be recommended that:

1. Measures should be taken by the government to reduce the rate and magnitude of unavoidable gas emissions caused by industrial activities.
2. Measures such as flare stacks, safety shutdown systems, and emergency depressurization systems should be properly adopted as enablers of gas mitigation for a cleaner environment and bequeathed to everyone living in the area for the socio-economic growth of the environment.
3. The government and policymakers in the oil industry should make every effort to reduce the quantity of gas emissions in the environment to protect lives.
4. There should be proper monitoring of the oil and gas companies' activities to guide its operations by the state government through the Ministry of Environment to give adequate

knowledge and understanding of the effects of gas emissions on the environment for a quick solution.

5. The establishment of a national regulatory framework on the environment and the provision of environmental laws and regulations will act as a guide to the company's operations and activities.

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